

Newsletter

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WELCOME TO THE 7th STRIKE PROJECT NEWSLETTER!

Stronger Training and Increased Knowledge for better Enforcement against Waste and Mercury - STRIKE project aims to further enhance operational activities and capacities of authorities involved in addressing illegal trade & management of problematic waste streams (e.g. e-waste, end-of-life vehicles, batteries & waste mercury), as well as illegal production & trade of mercury-added products (MAPs). Our newsletters are available at: <https://www.strikeproject.org/>

AREAS OF WORK

Enhanced knowledge and risk analysis of waste related crime and mercury-added products

To enhance knowledge and understanding of illegal trade and management of problematic waste streams (including in particular e-waste, ELVS, batteries and other mercury waste), and illegal production and trade of mercury-added products, in support of an improved risk analysis and possible harmonisation of national annual plans and enforcement strategies.

New tools and methodologies

To develop practical tools and advanced methodologies in support of practitioners across the compliance and enforcement chain, in their fight against waste and product trade crimes, including waste mercury and mercury-added products. Technical information generated during the project will be used to indicate product types and waste streams vulnerable for fraud and direct future compliance and enforcement activities.

Capacity building and skills acquisition

To enhance capacities and skills of practitioners and stakeholders in selected countries in Europe, as well as CEE/Balkans region Africa in the detection, investigation and prosecution of waste-crime cases and illegal trade in mercury-added products. This activity includes two main components: 1) the update and development of tailored-made tools and materials on waste and mercury-related crimes and 2) capacity building activities for practitioners, delivered both face-to-face (multidisciplinary training sessions) and online (webinars).

Learn more at: <https://www.strikeproject.org/>

STRIKE PARTNERS

The University of Limerick is the lead institution of the project consortium which is composed of four organizations ranging from UN Organizations to different research institutions and universities.

Click on the icons to discover more about each organization!

In addition to the project team, there are five Associate Partners that will support the project's activities, in particular: the [German Customs Authority](#); [District Government of Lower Bavaria](#); [Basel Convention Regional Centre](#) (Slovakia); [African Institute](#) (South Africa) and the [Waste Management Department of the Ministry of Environment and Physical Planning of Macedonia](#).

You can find more information about project partners here: <https://www.strikeproject.org/partners>

COMMUNICATION

Follow our account to be up to date with project news, trainings, activities...and share our contents!

Follow us on Twitter: [@STRIKE_EU](#)

Join our group on LinkedIn: [STRIKE: Stronger Training and Increased Knowledge for better Enforcement Waste & Mercury](#)

STRIKE UPDATES

Capacity building and skills acquisition

Multidisciplinary training sessions

➤ The project organized four **multi-disciplinary training courses** covering all steps in the enforcement chain (including inspection and detection, investigation, prosecution and sentencing). The trainings aimed to enhance national and international cooperation, and involve awareness raising webinar sessions to reach a global audience of practitioners. The training were originally meant to be organized in Germany, the Netherlands, Slovakia and Ireland, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic three were converted into online workshops, (Germany, Slovakia and Ireland), while the one in the Netherlands was conducted face-to-face. The sessions were designed upon the project outcomes and findings of the **Training Needs Assessment** and leveraged on the **Training Toolkit** developed within the project. The four online trainings were organized and successfully delivered to more than 350 participants throughout 2021 and 2022.

- **Germany Training (online): Illicit Management and illegal trade of problematic waste streams, mercury-added products; special focus: ship-breaking** (9-11 Nov 2021), organized by the German Police University (DHPol)
- **Slovakia Training (online): Better Enforcement against Waste and Mercury crime** (24-26 Nov 2021), organized by the Regional Centre of the Basel Convention for Training and Technology Transfer for Central and Eastern Europe in Bratislava
- **The Netherlands (face-to-face): Training: Essential Elements of Safety Guidelines, Development of Mercury Safety Tool and Training Video** (18th Nov 2021), organized by the Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI)
- **Ireland Training (online): Practical perspectives on waste enforcement planning and inspections with a focus on forensic and damages analysis relating to waste crime** (25-27 Jan 2022), organized by the University of Limerick (UL)

The presentations and tools used in those trainings were reunited under the webpage of the Strike Project (www.strikeproject.org). To inform about the upcoming trainings and to collect participants registration, news and online forms were created and uploaded on the Strike website and the information was largely distributed via the project's network (including the project mailing list) and on social media (including on LinkedIn and Twitter).

Key Outcomes From Our Training Programmes: Geographic Reach

350

Training participants

59

Countries
Represented

Final STRIKE Training on Practical perspectives on waste enforcement planning and inspections with a focus on forensic and damages analysis relating to waste crime and waste – Organized by University of Limerick [Online]

The University of Limerick (UL) is a higher education institution in Ireland. The Department of Electronic and Computer Engineering (ECE) within UL has an excellent reputation for producing high quality action-based research concerning the sustainability of electronics, in particular e-waste and has been a project partner and lead on several international e-waste studies including CWIT, DOTCOM and WasteForce. Recently, the department of ECE has studied the hazardous components of e-waste in more detail including plastics and hazardous components such as mercury added products.

This training focused on practical perspectives on waste enforcement planning and inspections with a focus on forensic and damages analysis relating to waste crime and waste. It was held on 3 half day sessions from 25-27 Jan 2022.

The training started with a practical focus on the inspection and detection of problematic wastes with a case study focussing on waste plastics. This covered various *modi operandi* of illicit waste shipments and included a broader conversation on the roots of illicit trade in plastics. Enforcement planning was covered in some detail with practical examples of the prioritisation of enforcement, risk analysis and the importance of intelligence and data collection.

To facilitate the breadth and depth of the expert guidance developed by the Netherlands Forensics Institute (NFI), the bulk of one day's training was dedicated to the demonstration of forensic tools, safety guidance and protocols. Further sessions focussed on intelligence gathering to assess the risk of mercury and e-waste crime through the use of inventories, and the state of mercury legislation, policies and the global perspective on mercury.

Two sessions covered environmental damages and their assessment in the prosecution of cases. In order to advance this agenda further in the enforcement network, the STRIKE team invited training regarding damages to the ecosphere, in particular assessment of damages on fauna. This is a major advancement in the true cost of waste crime.

All training materials can be found at the following page, with password restricted access: <https://www.strikeproject.org/trainings>

Webinars

STRIKE Webinar #8 - Quantifying e-waste: the key role of data and statistics

On **January 14th**, UNITAR SCYCLE organized a webinar specifically focusing on e-waste and the relevance of collecting statistics for proper risk assessment and enforcement planning. After introducing the project's concept and e-waste as a problematic waste stream, the webinar provided an interesting overview of the findings of the global and regional e-waste monitors and the methodology applied to collect sound and comparable data. Two presentations followed focussing on used electronics export from Ireland and quantifying e-waste on scrap metals. Presentations delivered during the webinar are available at: <https://www.strikeproject.org/webinars>

STRIKE Webinar #9 Road Inspections: Best practices

The last STRIKE webinar was organised on **January 19th**, with a specific focus on best practices in road inspections. The webinar, delivered by Mr. Erwin Verheuge, former Chief Inspector within the Belgian Federal Police, was restricted to representatives from the law enforcement and customs authorities.

STRIKE FINAL CONFERENCE: Achievements and Lessons Learned

On **February 9th**, the STRIKE Final conference “Achievements and Lessons Learned” was organised online and opened by Prof. Norelee Kennedy, Vice President of Research at the University of Limerick (UL), Professor Colin Fitzpatrick (UL) and Ms. Vittoria Luda di Cortemiglia (UNITAR). To reflect the final conference aims “to promote and ensure the sustainability and use of the project results with a wider public”, the conference provided an opportunity to present the final results of the project, strengthen networking initiatives, and exploring follow-up activities to sustain the project outcomes.

The conference was divided into three sections. These sections were 1. Conference Opening: Project STRiKE & Panel Discussion, 2. Problematic Waste Streams & Solutions Developed through STRiKE, and finally, 3. Legacy: Passing the Resources Forwards. All partners contributed.

Two keynote speakers from the Basel, Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions Secretariat and the Minamata Convention Secretariat, Ms. Tatiana Terekhova and Mr. Eisaku Toda, were invited to present the latest developments related to hazardous wastes and mercury. In the afternoon session, Major Gianluca Muscatello and Dr Sara Ferrandi presented the achievements of the [OPFA Waste Project](#), while Ms. Annouchka Mathieu provided an update on the [Ambitus project](#). Finally, DG Environment provided the closing address, highlighting key changes to the Waste Shipment Regulations.

In total, 108 people, 61 women and 46 men registered to attend the final conference. 39 countries were represented.

STRIKE Overview Video:

On the occasion of the final conference the STRIKE Overview video was presented. Have a look at it here: <https://vimeo.com/671909620> The video is also available with subtitles in [Russian](#), [French](#), [Spanish](#)

Meet our H-LAB Members

The STRIKE Project is happy to introduce to you individually a High-Level Advisory Board H-LAB Member.

Dana Lapesova – Basel Convention Regional Centre (BCRC) Slovakia

Dana Lapešová has been working as Director of the Basel Convention Regional Centre (BCRC) Slovakia since 2002. Her role is to assist countries from Central and Eastern Europe with adoption and implementation of the Basel Convention principles into their national legislations. The BCRC, with its experiences in cooperation within the region and bridging role between project partners and Central and Eastern Europe, is a relevant associated partner in the STRIKE project team. Ms. Lapesova has organized more than 30 regional workshops and trainings and coordinated several projects on environmentally sound management for different waste streams, such as e-waste, used batteries and used oils. She coordinated assistance in legislation preparation and supported synergies among hazardous wastes and chemicals conventions (i.e. Basel, Rotterdam and Stockholm). As a BCRC representative she is

a member of different working groups and partnership programmes under the umbrella of the Basel Convention and UNEP. These include Partnership on Action on computing Equipment (PACE), Expert working group, Household waste partnership, and ENFORCE (on transboundary movement of hazardous waste).